

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON THE SOCIO-ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This article examines the aspects of the development and impact of the digital economy, the impact of digital technologies on the economic life of society, and the corresponding changes due to innovation, the introduction of AI and new business models. Digitalization is changing society, our concepts of success and accelerated pace are forcing us to reconsider social attitudes and habits. The introduction of digital technologies in government structures and organizations radically changes legislation and requires close attention and qualitative structural changes. Issues of morality and ethics, support for socially vulnerable segments of the population in a changing reality with the introduction of a digital system everywhere, including in the range of social services, need to be studied and worked out. By combining the efforts of the state, business, society, we can achieve a significant improvement in the position of digitalization of our country, which in turn will lead to an improvement in the overall well-being of our economy.

Key words: digital economy, state, society, social support, AI.

O'ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING IJTIMOYIY- IQTISODIYOTGA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyotning rivojlanishi va ta'siri, raqamli texnologiyalarning jamiyat iqtisodiy hayotiga ta'siri, innovatsiyalar tufayli tegishli o'zgarishlar, AI va yangi biznes modellarini joriy etish masalalari o'rganib o'tilishi ko'rib o'tilishi mumkin. Raqamlashtirish jamiyatni o'zgartirmoqda, muvaffaqiyat haqidagi tasavvurlarimiz va tezlashtirilgan sur'atlar bizni ijtimoiy qarashlar va odatlarni qayta ko'rib chiqishga majbur qilmoqda. Davlat tuzilmalari va tashkilotlarida raqamli texnologiyalarning joriy etilishi qonun hujjatlarini tubdan o'zgartiradi hamda diqqat va sifat jihatidan tarkibiy o'zgarishlarni talab etadi. Axloq va odob-axloq masalalari, aholining ijtimoiy zaif segmentlarini qo'llab-quvvatlash hamma joyda, shu jumladan ijtimoiy xizmatlar doirasida raqamli tizimni joriy etish bilan o'zgarib borayotgan haqiqat sharoitida o'rganilishi va ishlab chiqilishi kerak. Davlat, biznes va jamiyat sa'y-harakatlarini birlashtirish orqali mamlakatimizni raqamlashtirish pozitsiyasini sezilarli darajada yaxshilashga erishishimiz mumkin, bu esa o'z navbatida iqtisodiyotimizning umumiy farovonligining yaxshilanishiga olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli iqtisodiyot, davlat, jamiyat, ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash, AI.

Introduction.

The digital economy is perceived by society today as a means, a way to solve almost any problem, this is easy to see from the number of studies in the social, economic and humanitarian sciences that are now being conducted in all countries of our world, in public disputes, we see how legislation is changing and supplementing, politicians are conducting serious debates on this topic, and the Internet is full of explanations on this topic. But we need to understand that the digital economy is closely linked with other sciences, moreover, it is impossible to consider digitalization separately without society, for which this system was created and developed. And perception in the context of a full understanding of why we need the digital economy, how it can serve humanity, what are the pros and cons, how to optimize the processes of full application of this knowledge – we must work out,

understand and solve all these issues not only for ourselves, but also for our future generation.

Literature review.

The main statistical information is taken from the Internet, the database of the Google Scholar system is used, the article also uses data and statistics of national sites, articles and abstracts of foreign resources (journal The Guardian, Algorithm Watch), for the necessary addition and to provide reliable examples. The information directly used in this article on the challenges and problems associated with the with the introduction of the digital economy into the lives of our compatriots, about the social sector as the most vulnerable in every state system.

Research methodology.

The methodological base of the study is represented by theoretical provisions. As a basic research method, the author uses a logical and structural analysis of theoretical statistics provided in the public domain. The main methods are analysis and synthesis, which allow us to show the results of the study, and draw conclusions about the trend in the development of the digital economy in our country as one of the drivers of the modern world on the example of countries such as Spain, Great Britain and others.

Discussion and result.

Rice. 1 Features in the classification of the digital economy.

Digitalization has reached a new level, and companies that have staked on the development of their company in this segment have become global giants. Facebook, Amazon, Apple, Alibaba Group, Microsoft, and a host of other companies in this direction are among the first companies in the world by market capitalization. As indicated in the article "Digital Economy: Problems and Prospects" by T.V. Lyubavin, today the United States and China are the leaders of the digital economy, and are included in the list of the richest countries in the world with a high GDP. This, in turn, is characterized by the high development of the market and market relations, as well as the well-being of the population of these countries⁵⁸.

It is worth noting that the development of the digital economy is not quite uniform as we can imagine. There are countries where digitalization is in its infancy, according to a report by the ITU (International Telecommunication Union), in the poor countries of our planet, where 14 percent of the population lives, only 407 million people used the Internet⁵⁹, and vice versa, for example, in the People's Republic of China there is an "Internet within the Internet", a kind of national digital space, the number of people who constantly use the Internet is 750 million people. The approach of our government is a timely and accurate diagnosis of the future, because it is digitalization and new technologies, innovations that lead states to future development and improvement in all spheres of life, make it possible to save huge

⁵⁸ Lyubavina T. V. Digital Economy: Problems and Prospects. – 2022. – T. 772. – P. 4

⁵⁹ <https://news.un.org/ru/story/2023/03/1438342>

reserves of energy and time and keep up in development compared to other countries of the world⁶⁰.

At the same time, the uniqueness of the digital economy is that it is multinational. Many countries seek to protect their Internet space at the state level, at the same time there is a simplification, standardization of the technical component and rules in this area.

Artificial intelligence, the development of social networks, the smartphone at the level of assistant and friend, the spread of technology – all these digital changes at the level of government organizations and large industrial enterprises to small firms and corporations – have radically changed our lives and basic concepts have also undergone changes. The age of progress and technology and now the transition is not smooth and years have passed before people have time to get used to changes - new times require speed of perception. Like the new Iphone, which is updated in its line every year, so we must get used to the fact that constant changes are our today's reality. Effective development of markets is possible only if there is constant optimization and improvement of technologies, so it is worth paying attention to changes in higher education institutions and institutes. That is, the training of personnel with deep knowledge of digital technologies, and the creation of regulatory documentation for the regulation of digital markets. When looking at the prospects, the work of Kate Raworth of the University of Oxford is interesting. The only goal that the modern economy pursues is the goal of continuous growth. In this regard, the current economy is a flow of cyclical income between the state, enterprise, banks, government and trade. Kate Raworth redefines the foundations of the economy and creates a safe space for humanity that includes a social basis⁶¹.

The main task of social support, as we know, is to reduce poverty and social inequality, which means free access to existing benefits for people who are entitled to these payments, and assistance to the poor. The World Bank has a long history of

⁶⁰ Usmanhodzhaeva S. DIGITAL TRANSFORMATIONS OF SERVICE SECTOR ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN // Iqtisodiy taraqqiyot va tahlil. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 6. – P. 242-248.

⁶¹ Pavlova I. V., Moiseev V. O. Digital Economy: Problems and Prospects. – 2019. – №. 11. – P. 63-63.

eradicating poverty in the world, providing financial and technical support to developing countries to achieve the goal of reducing poverty within a generation. Over the past three decades, there has been a gradual decline in the number of people living in extreme poverty around the world. The consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent negative impact on the economy, social sphere and health of the world's population have increased the number of people below the poverty line⁶². The crises and diseases of recent years have dealt a significant blow to the trajectory of our world's movement towards the goal of no poor people left on the planet by 2030.

Rice. 2. World Bank data, average annual growth rate per capita, real survey, average consumption or income, total population⁶³.

Recommendations and analysis of the systems of our state by independent rating agencies makes it possible to form an opinion about the state of our country in this aspect, and determines the image in front of other countries. The high rating of various independent agencies makes it possible to integrate into the world

⁶² Peresyphkin D. I. ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION IN THE CONTEXT OF THE CORONAVIRUS INFECTION PANDEMIC. – 2020. – P. 5631-5633.

⁶³ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SI.SPR.PC40.ZG>

community, setting a high bar for achieving the goals of being called a state with an independent democratic society, socially protected, economically developed⁶⁴.

In Uzbekistan, as of 2024, the official level indicator for determining the poverty line has been increased by 9.3 percent, according to the report of the Statistics Agency under the President of Uzbekistan, and amounts to 621 thousand soums per person per month (20.7 thousand soums per 1 person per day)⁶⁵. The poverty rate in our country decreased from 24% in 2000 to 11.5% in 2020, now about 18.% of the adult population, which is 2.2 million adults living below the poverty line⁶⁶.

How can digitalization and the digital economy help in the field of social services and support for the poor? In our country, this area is just being formed, so it is premature to say anything specific, but it is possible to consider and compare the prospects for the use of digitalization of services with the current state of affairs⁶⁷. In each mahalla, notebooks of social protection of "women's", "youth", and the "Generosity and Support" fund have been created. But we can definitely say that there is no coordination of actions in this case. The process of obtaining social protection and benefits is complex in itself, and most importantly, the population is not sufficiently informed about social support measures. Currently, the system of social support is undergoing reform - a single portal my.gov.uz has been created, and services to the population in the social sphere are also provided automatically. The EPIGU (Unified Portal of Interactive Public Services), also working online, provides the opportunity to apply online for child benefits and financial assistance. Such work should be carried out with all types of social services provided by the state. Lonely elderly people, disabled people of various groups, orphans, low-income families, all these categories should be entered in the appropriate registers and regularly receive notifications about the status of their account, about their status and changes in it, about new regulations and decrees regarding this category of the population. Potential

⁶⁴ Usmankhodjaeva S. M. ON PROBLEMS IN IMPROVING THE POSITIONS OF UZBEKISTAN IN INTERNATIONAL RATINGS AND INDICES: THEORY, PRACTICE AND STRATEGY. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. Special Issue 13. – P. 630-633.

⁶⁵ <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2024/01/22/mpr/>

⁶⁶ <https://uz.kursiv.media/2024-03-07/v-uzbekistane-bolee-4-mln-chelovek-prozhivaet-za-chertoj-bednosti/>

⁶⁷ <https://uznews.uz/posts/71764>

problems of information social services are data leakage, people who simply cannot enter their data into the register in a timely manner, lack of information about this service, "refuseniks" living within remote areas who are unable to enter their data. To eliminate this kind of problem, it is necessary to establish a kind of control system that will register, keep records, refuse support to illegal participants, and deal with the consequences of events. All data will be confidential. Banks and their systems can help in this process, since bank employees who have been using online services for a long time know perfectly well how to establish work with confidential information and maintain a control system. For example, let's take the UK - this country has been a leader in digitalization since 2016. The Department for Work and Pensions (NDTP) prefers a system of intellectual developments in social security. The Department employs AIs that conduct monitoring, analytics, and make decisions based on the analysis made. Automation has led to significant savings in the work of the department, and at the same time, the speed of public service has increased and the reliability of the collected information has increased significantly. At the same time, experts argue that the use of AI and digitalization, and then the full automation of the definition of well-being and the assessment of people's well-being, raise the question of the ethical component for society. Journalist E. Pilkington⁶⁸ in a series of articles "The Poverty Algorithm" says that after digitalization is completed at the social level, the poor will become poorer, because machines do not have emotions, and they do not know empathy. Instead of compassion, they will simply withdraw the last money from your card, as many banking systems are already doing, collecting debts from their customers. that feedback is almost impossible, and challenging the AI is a difficulty in reversing an illegal decision, and there is a huge difficulty in correcting errors. An example of such an error is the power outage in Spain that occurred in 2019, with more than half a million people losing their lighting benefits due to an AI failure. The authorities are still suing the population, while refusing to provide defense lawyers with the source code of the system to check the failure⁶⁹.

⁶⁸ Pilkington E. [Digital dystopia: Algorithms punish the poor](#) // The Guardian.

⁶⁹ Kayser-Bril N. [Spain: Legal fight over an algorithm's code](#) // Algorithm Watch.

Risks and challenges are also carried by the technological features of digitalization.

According to the UN, up to 100 million tons of electronic waste are produced in the world every year, and no more than 20 percent of it is recycled. With the development of technological progress, this figure will only grow, and we are well aware of this. Technological vulnerability – blackouts, for example, can stop the activities of almost all enterprises today, since dependence on technology is now ubiquitous. the rise of cybercrime. At a press conference at the AIMC with the participation of employees of the Cybersecurity Center of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, it was reported that the number of cybercrimes in 2023 was only 5.5 thousand compared to 2020, when the number of such crimes was only 106⁷⁰.

The challenges and threats to the development of the digital economy need to be addressed in a step-by-step and comprehensive manner. We need help and support from the state, business and, of course, the public. First of all, the creation and scaling of digital platforms for business. Formation of cybersecurity systems. Supporting small and medium-sized businesses, it is here, in this environment, that startups arise as the main engines of innovation and non-standard solutions. We all remember how the creators of Facebook and Alibaba started, so ideas should be able to come to life. The training of specialists in the digital economy and the IT sphere is a priority, the future of our economy is in the hands of these young people.

Findings.

The digital economy, we can say with confidence, is a driver of growth, development and progress of the economy as a whole. This is also due to the service market, which is also developing aggressively, and the provision of quality service is now of great importance to the consumer. Thanks to technologies and the use of AI, costs have become minimal, and the eternal question of price and quality of a product or service, when comparing the methods of the traditional economy and the digital economy, of course, the digital economy will look more attractive. Digitalization

⁷⁰ <https://uz.kursiv.media/2023-12-20/v-2023-m-v-uzbekistane-bylo-soversheno-55-tys-kiberprestuplenij/#:~:text=In%202023%2Dm%20in%20Uzbekistan,cybercrimes&text=President%20Uzbekistan%20Shavkat%20Mirziyoyev%20,cybercrimes.>

covers more and more areas in our society, and the development and digitalization of the social services sector is ahead, which causes fair debates and disputes - the issue of ethics in giving decision-making to an automaton instead of a person causes anger and indignation among many segments of our society. It is assumed that over time, the issues and challenges we are currently facing will be solved in stages and systematically, taking into account all stakeholders.

Despite the fact that our republic is not in a leading position in terms of development, every year our country confidently improves its performance. In the work to improve and optimize the digital economy, it is necessary to pay attention to the challenges and risks, increase support for entrepreneurs, nurture personnel from the younger generation in the field of IT technologies, and make it a habit to constantly grow and develop, following the trends of the time. And, of course, special attention should be paid to the social sector, as a state that supports the course for equality of all segments of the population, opposes discrimination of all kinds, supports and cares about the weakest category of the country's population - the socially unprotected stratum - and make every effort to help and adapt to the changing reality of our compatriots.

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